

IN-SITU EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF INTERFACIAL TOUGHNESS OF ALUMINUM THIN FILMS ON POLYIMIDE SUBSTRATES

Emanuele Cattarinuzzi¹, Riccardo Lucchini¹, Dario Gastaldi¹, Pasquale Vena^{1,2}, Leandro Lorenzelli³
and Johan P. M. Hoefnagels⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Materials and Chemical Engineering, Laboratory of Biological Structure Mechanics (LaBS), Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

Email: emanuele.cattarinuzzi@polimi.it, web page: <http://www.labsmech.polimi.it/>

²IRCCS, Istituto Ortopedico Galeazzi,
via R. Galeazzi 4, 20161 Milano, Italy

Email: pasquale.vena@polimi.it, web page: <http://www.galeazzi-gsd.it/>

³Microsystems Technology Research Unit, Fondazione Bruno Kessler
Via Sommarive 18, 38123 Povo, Trento, Italy

Email: lorenzel@fbk.eu, web page: <http://mst.fbk.eu/>

⁴Department of Mechanical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology
P.O. Box 513, 5600 MB Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Email: J.P.M.hoefnagels@tue.nl, web page: <https://www.tue.nl/>

Keywords: Thin films, Interfacial delamination, Peel test, In-situ characterization

ABSTRACT

Interfacial delamination embodies a major issue as concerns the mechanical reliability of metal-on-polymer thin films. The interfacial toughness of a metal/polymer material system is a relevant constraint when dealing with the design of electronic devices, which feature stacks of several dissimilar materials. This evidence provides the motivations for the experimental measurement of metal/polymer adhesion.

In this study, the interfacial delamination of Aluminum thin films on Polyimide substrates has been investigated combining in-situ light microscopy with a miniaturized 90° peel test setup. Being peel forces in the mN range, dedicated clamps have been designed in order to avoid the use of conventional sliding fixtures meanwhile ensuring proper 90° peel geometry when testing samples on a uniaxial tensile stage. Peel tests revealed a very sharp delamination front, with no evidences of interface heterogeneities. In-situ imaging allowed to interpret the trend of the force/displacement curve. Meaningful data for the computation of the fracture energy ($\sim 90 \text{ J/m}^2$) were clearly distinguished from data affected by undesired dissipation phenomena competing with delamination, such as plastic deformation of the Aluminum film.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since several years the electronics industry features an extensive use of thin films in the form of stacks of dissimilar materials. Demanding performances often translate into increasingly complex architecture assemblies of metallic and non-metallic films. In turns, to ensure the mechanical reliability of modern electronic devices for a reasonably long service life becomes more and more challenging. The composite nature of modern devices is inherently susceptible to severe stress conditions not only due to accidental drops, while also during normal operation. In the field of microelectronics, mechanical stresses are usually an indirect consequence of configuration misfits caused by driving forces from a different physics. Residual stresses may be induced by temperature fluctuations in the presence of different thermal expansion coefficients or by epitaxial growth on a

crystalline material layer with a different lattice structure [1]. Interface delamination is one of the most frequent failure mechanisms through which adjacent layers release misfit stresses [2], resulting in a drift from the nominal electronic performances. For this reason, the microelectronics industry is very sensitive to the issue of thin films delamination.

More recently, the research towards flexible and stretchable macroelectronics raised mechanical performances (such as large strains compatibility) to the list of primary requirements of a device [3-6]. Deformable electrodes and interconnects can be achieved exploiting the enhanced ductility exhibited by metal thin films on compliant polymeric substrates [7]: Li and Suo [8] discussed the role of the polymer layer as a mean to prevent strain localization in the metal film when entering the plastic deformation regime. When strain delocalization is achieved, ductile failure mechanisms (such as necking) are suppressed, improving the deformation capabilities of the metal film. Nevertheless, in the event of delamination at the metal/polymer interface, the metal film becomes free-standing and all the aforementioned benefits vanish [9]. For this reason, interface delamination embodies a major issue as concerns the mechanical reliability of deformable electronics devices based on metal/polymer thin films.

Reliable design requires characterization of material properties: adhesion can be tested in several ways, but not all of them are suitable to go beyond a qualitative comparison between different interfaces [10]. Being metal/polymer thin films comparable to flexible laminates, peel tests are widely accepted as a suitable technique for the quantitative assessment of the adhesive fracture energy [11]. In 90° peel tests, the work provided by external forces to induce delamination (*Work Of Separation*, WOS) can be equated to the mode I fracture energy [12]. In order to ensure a 90° angle between delaminating layers, experimental setups are usually equipped with low-friction sliding fixtures [13]. When testing adhesion for microelectronics and deformable macroelectronics, characteristic dimensions of samples may be significantly small, with expected peel forces in the mN range [14], thus even sliders with very low friction coefficients may introduce measurement artefacts in the force signal. To cope with this issue, one possibility is to use a uniaxial stage and orient the peel direction at an angle of 45° with respect to the clamp displacement direction. Previous work by van der Sluis and co-workers [15] provides an example of this strategy when dealing with ductile interfaces for stretchable electronics. Specifically, the adhesion of 18 μm thick Copper (Cu) layers on Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was measured. In-situ imaging of the local peel front was also performed by adding a digital camera to the setup.

One of the benefits related to in-situ imaging (especially, in-situ microscopy) is the investigation of the interface mechanics at different length scales. Neggers and co-workers [16] performed peel tests with in-situ scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to investigate the adhesion of Cu films on thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) and PDMS. The in-situ analysis revealed the heterogeneous nature of the peel front, featuring elastomeric fibrils drawn from the bulk PDMS by the asperities of the Cu layer. The relation between the macroscopic interface strength and the roughness of the Cu layer was then elucidated as a combination of mechanical interlocking and fibrillation at the microscale.

In-situ imaging can also support the identification of a suitable modeling strategy. In the assumption of homogenous interfaces, experimental results should be independent of sample dimensions and could be safely plugged into continuum models like cohesive traction/separation laws [17]. In reality, all interfaces are heterogeneous at a certain length scale, thus the use of continuum models is suitable as far as scale separation holds between interface heterogeneities and the application length scale. As shown in the work by Neggers [16], the characteristic dimension of interface heterogeneities can be estimated by in-situ imaging and, depending on the expected application, multi-scale modeling should be preferred to cohesive modeling alone in order to account for scale effects which would be otherwise neglected [18].

Besides the identification of microscale phenomena of physical interest, in-situ imaging can also provide a meaningful support to the post-processing of measured data. In a peel test, in fact, the work done by external forces can be correlated with the interface fracture energy only as long as the delamination enters the steady-state propagation regime. This means that new free-surface is created at a constant rate, directly related to the clamp displacement rate. The schematic picture is that of a process zone of fixed dimensions, which shifts unaltered along the sample length as the test proceeds (Fig. 1.a). Ideally, steady-state delamination is only preceded by a tensile loading of the peel arm up to

the critical delamination force. Such a transient response can be clearly distinguished from the steady-state propagation directly by the trend of force/displacement data (Fig. 1.b). Conversely, when competing dissipation mechanisms accompany delamination, temporary fluctuations of the force signal can be recorded even when steady-state delamination is expected, and the interpretation of the force/displacement data may be not straightforward unless combined with in-situ imaging [19]. In this work, in-situ light microscopy (LM) was used in order to investigate the delamination of Aluminum/Polyimide (Al/PI) thin films upon 90° peel. A clear correspondence was found between the morphology of the peel front and the trend of the force/displacement curve. Among the full set of measurements, in-situ imaging allowed to discern between meaningful data for the computation of the fracture energy and data affected by undesired dissipation phenomena competing with delamination.

Figure 1: (a) sketch of the peel front during steady-state delamination. A clamp displacement increment equal to Δu_{peel} results in the creation of new surface equal to $b \times \Delta u_{peel}$ (green rectangles); (b) typical force/displacement curve in a peel test, where the transient response (red-shaded region) can be clearly distinguished from the steady-state response. The green rectangle corresponds to the energy dissipated to create new surface over a displacement increment equal to Δu_{peel} .

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The application meant for the Al/PI material system here presented is that of metal/polymer deformable interconnects featuring a metal line width between 10 and 50 μm [20,21]. Although it is generally recommended to design peel samples resembling typical application length scales [10], practical issues like sample handling and clamping cannot be neglected in order to ensure the feasibility of the test. As a good match between the aforementioned requirements, a width of 1 mm was adopted for Al/PI peel samples. Retrospective evaluation of this choice was enabled by in-situ LM, verifying the actual homogeneity of the peel front.

2.1 Materials

The polymer substrate consisted in a commercial PI (Durimide® DI115A, Fujifilm) spin coated on Si wafers aiming at a target thickness of 10 μm . Rectangular strips of Al thin film (1 μm thickness) were obtained on the top of PI by means of a lift-off procedure. A detailed description of samples micro-fabrication can be found in [20]. The final in-plane design of the peel samples featured an Al strip of 1x15 mm² surrounded by a frame of PI with a width of 150 μm (Fig 2.a-e).

2.2 Clamp design and preparation

Due to the small sample size, peel forces were expected to be in the mN range, thus any sliding fixture system for 90° peel was rejected. Conversely, a downscaled version of the approach described by van der Sluis [15] was devised in order to ensure a 90° geometry during the tests. A plate of Al with a thickness of 1 mm (i.e., equal to the width of the Al film featured by the peel samples) was cut at an angle of 45°, obtaining a pair of complementary wedges.

Figure 2: (a) wafer for sample storage; (b) peel sample; (c-e) procedure to single out the peel sample with a sharp knife; (f-l) sketch of the clamps and the strategy devised to perform 90° peel test by means of a uniaxial tensile equipment.

The proposed approach, then, reads as follows: the top surface of the Al film is glued along the side of the 45° cut of one wedge (Fig. 2.f). Thereafter, the complementary wedge is faced to the sample and one end of the PI substrate is glued to a proper spot on the complementary wedge (Fig. 2.g-h). The negligible bending stiffness of the PI substrate ensures that, when the wedges are moved apart, the PI is pulled at an angle of 90° with respect to the plane where the sample sits (Fig. 2.i-l). The PI, then, serves as the peel arm of a 90° peel test.

Ideally, the surface of the wedge which provides full support to the Al layer should be perfectly flat. In reality this is never the case. The practical risk is that, when facing the sample to the wedge, the Al film gets wrinkled onto the asperities of wedge surface. Thus, the roughness of the wedge surface should be way lower than the thickness of the Al layer, aiming indeed at the roughness of the Al film itself. For this reason, the side of the wedges was prepared by a sequence of sandpaper grinding and polishing with diamond suspension, until a mirror-reflective surface was achieved. The roughness of the wedge surface and the Al film was measured by means of 3D optical profilometry (Plμ2300, Sensofar). A root-mean-square roughness (R_{rms}) of about 50 nm was obtained in both cases, thus the wedge surface was judged suitably smooth to behave as a flat support (Fig. 3.a)

2.3 Preparation of the sample assembly

A bi-component epoxy glue for metal/metal bonding was used (Kombi Metal/Metal, Bison) to fully constrain the top surface of the Al film to the wedge. The whole system (from now on referred to as *sample assembly*) was then clamped and kept compressed for a curing time of 24 h. After curing, the whole sample assembly was gently grinded on both sides in order to get rid of the excessive epoxy glue and exhibit, at a microscopic inspection, the correct stack of layers (wedge/glue/Al/PI, Fig 3.b). As it can be noticed from Figure 3.b, the sample assembly featured multiple interfaces. In order to be sure to test the Al/PI interface, a pre-crack was artificially initiated driving the tip of sharp tweezers right at the interface of interest. Once the pre-crack was initiated, a short segment of PI was also obtained, to be used as a starting point for the peel arm.

Figure 3: (a) comparison between the roughness of Al film and the wedge surface after grinding and polishing; (b) side of the sample assembly after grinding. The inset shows the stack of layers featuring the sample assembly, i.e., wedge/glue/Al/PI.

2.3 Experimental setup

Samples were clamped on a micro-tensile stage with a displacement resolution of 1 μm (Tension/compression module, Kammrath and Weiss GmbH). The peel force was measured by means of a single-ended beam load cell with 1 mN resolution (KD45, ME-Meßsysteme). For practical reasons and differently from the case of van der Sluis [15], the load cell was oriented in the clamp displacement direction. To establish the relation between the load cell signal and the peel force, dedicated calibration was performed applying known dead weights at an angle 45° by means of an adjustable pulley.

Clamping of the sample assembly was performed under a stereomicroscope. The angle between the clamp displacement direction and that of the Al film was checked in order to achieve a 45° target value. After facing the complementary wedge to the sample assembly, the PI peel arm was glued as schematically depicted in Figure 2.h. A commercial cyanoacrylate glue (Loctite® 406™) was used for this purpose.

Figure 4: (a) detail of the 45° wedges mounted on the setup; (b) sample image of the 90° peel configuration achieved upon uniaxial displacement of the tensile stage; (c) overview of the experimental setup including the tensile stage and the stereomicroscopes for in-situ LM; (d) sample image captured by the in-situ top view; (e) sample image captured by the in-situ side view.

In-situ LM imaging was pursued by means of two stereomicroscopes (Stemi 2000, Zeiss), each of them equipped with a digital camera (AxioCam, Zeiss) and properly oriented in order to image the peel front both from the side and from the top (Fig. 4.c). The top view served as a check, to assess whether the global angle between the PI peel arm and the Al film kept at 90° (Fig. 4.d). The side view was meant to investigate the morphology of the peel front during the test (Fig. 4.e).

The clamp displacement rate was constant and set to 10 µm/s. The force/displacement data and the images captured by the side microscope were matched in order to identify the steady-state response of the sample when nothing but delamination was taking place at the peel front. Assuming the peel arm deformation to be fully elastic, the WOS can be measured as the ratio between the mean peel force in steady-state and the width of the sample [12].

$$\text{WOS} = F_{\text{peel}}/b \quad (1)$$

where F_{peel} is the peel force, b is the width of the sample. Considering the geometry of the test, the peel displacement, u_{peel} , to be plotted against peel force was measured as follows

$$u_{\text{peel}} = u_{\text{clamp}} \cos(\pi/4) \quad (2)$$

where u_{clamp} corresponds to the clamp displacement.

3 RESULTS

The peel angle, α_p , measured by the in-situ top view was equal to 92.5° (Fig. 4.d). With reference to the sketch of Figure 2.g-l, a peel angle bigger than 90° suggests that the peel arm was slightly longer than the corresponding delaminated length. Considering the stiffness of the PI (~5 GPa), it is unlikely that this was due to a significant deformation of the peel arm upon peel forces below 100 mN (see Fig. 5.a). It is more reasonable that the peel arm was slightly loose when glued to the complementary wedge. As compared to the ideal case of conformal contact depicted in Figure 2.i, this provided some extra-length which resulted in a small drift from the target peel angle.

The peel force was not completely constant during delamination (Fig. 5.a). The in-situ side view revealed a clear correlation between the trend of force/displacement data and the peel front morphology. To illustrate this, a representative measurement subset is reported in Figure 5. Fluctuating values of the force signal were measured when extensive plastic deformation of the Al thin film was imaged at the peel front (Fig. 5.a-b, left panel). This phenomena was triggered by undesired failure of the glue between the Al film and the wedge. Lacking support from the wedge, the Al film became free-standing and got pulled together with the peel arm. As a result, Al/PI interface delamination was accompanied by significant plastic dissipation of the Al film, requiring extra-energy to be provided by external forces. Conversely, constant values of peel forces were measured when a sharp delamination front was imaged (Fig. 5.a-b, right panel). When full support was provided by the wedge, the delaminated surface of the Al film was mostly flat, featuring mirror-like reflectivity (Fig. 5.b, right panel). In this conditions, it is reasonable to state that delamination was the sole dissipation mechanism at the peel front.

As anticipated, the mark left by competing dissipation mechanisms was embodied by a permanent blistering pattern on the Al film surface. Thus, ex-situ topography (LEXT OLS4100, Olympus) of the sample surface was performed and used as a further support to the interpretation of force/displacement data (Fig. 5.c-d). A good match was found between the extent of the blistered surface and the peel displacement corresponding to fluctuating force values. Same arguments hold for the correspondence between flat regions and constant peel forces.

Figure 5 summarizes the procedure to match force/displacement data, in-situ LM and ex-situ topography. Only force data corresponding to a sharp peel front were used to compute the WOS, which was measured to be 92±12 J/m².

Figure 5: (a) representative subset of force/displacement data. On the right axis, the WOS of separation is computed using equation (1) and a sample width of about 700 μm ; (b) comparison between the morphology of the peel front in the presence of extensive plastic deformation of the Al film (left panel) and when delamination only occurs (right panel); (c) height map and (d) corresponding reflected intensity image of the Al surface after peel. The comparison between the sub-figures within the same panel shows the match between the trend of force/displacement data and the morphology of the Al surface experiencing delamination.

4 DISCUSSIONS

4.1 On the reliability of the measured *Work Of Separation*

According to the in-situ side view, the peel front was extremely sharp with no evidences of heterogeneities. It can be argued, then, that resizing peel samples with respect to the application length scale was an eligible choice (see Chapter 2). Also, this evidence supports the approach proposed by Lucchini [22], who addressed the modeling of Al/PI interface delamination by means of cohesive elements rather than multi-scale modeling. Indeed, the smallest width of deformable interconnects meant for the Al/PI material system is $10\ \mu\text{m}$ [20, 21], meaning about 5 pixels with the magnification and resolution of the LM in-situ images here presented (Fig. 5.b). Higher magnification imaging and deeper focus capabilities would be more suitable to assess whether the homogeneity of the interface holds down to such length scales. This will be addressed in future work by means of in-situ SEM imaging.

Computing the WOS as reported in equation (1) implies that all the deformation taking place at the peel arm is assumed to be elastic. If so, when unloading the peel arm, the PI layer should appear perfectly flat as it was before testing. Conversely, ex-situ inspections revealed a residual curvature in the peel arm (Fig. 6.a-b), indicating the presence of permanent deformations and residual stresses. Such a curled configuration is that of a typical residual strain field due to bending. As explained by Kinloch and co-workers [23], the root of the peel arm undergoes bending and reversed bending in the vicinity of the peel front. Depending on the local radius of curvature, related stresses might be high enough to induce yielding in the peel arm. The plastic deformation of the peel arm is also a dissipation mechanism which accompanies steady-state delamination, thus current WOS results overestimate the interface toughness of the Al/PI material system. Kawashita and co-workers [11] proposed a method to estimate the contribution of the peel arm plasticity based on the analysis of the local peel geometry (e.g., root rotation, α_0 , and radius of curvature at the root, R_0). This will be addressed in future work, on the basis of the images captured by the in-situ top view (Fig. 6.c).

Figure 6: (a-b) residual curvature of the PI peel arm after testing; (c) root rotation, α_0 , and radius of curvature, R_0 , at the root of the peel arm subjected to local bending, as revealed by the in-situ top view.

4.2 On the origin of weak regions at the Al/glue interface

As anticipated, the plasticity of the Al thin film during peel occurred due to an undesired failure of the underlying epoxy glue (Fig. 7.a-b). This suggests the presence of some heterogeneous regions at the Al/glue interface, resulting in a locally weaker constraint of the Al film. Indeed, by carefully inspecting the stack of interfaces featured by the sample assembly, the presence of some local cavities was revealed in the epoxy glue layer (Fig. 7.c-d). These are likely due to air bubbles trapped in the glue during the mixing procedure, which was performed at atmospheric pressure. When the cavities emerge at the interface and meet the Al film, the latter experiences a complete lack of support (Fig. 7.d). Now, let us consider the delamination front advancing through the Al/PI interface. When a region with underlying cavities is met, the latter acts as a crack initiation site at the Al/glue interface, causing the Al film to become locally free-standing. In this configuration, the Al film gets stretched together with the PI peel arm and undergoes extensive plastic deformation. Nevertheless, the cohesive strength

of the Al film must be higher than the interface strength between Al and PI, since delamination at the target interface eventually occurs and fracture of the Al film upon stretch is practically never observed.

As a general recommendation, degassing when mixing the epoxy glue is suggested, in order to decrease the probability to trap air bubbles in the bi-component mixture.

Figure 7: (a) reflected intensity image and (b) corresponding height map of residual blistering patterns on the Al surface after peel; (c-d) detail of the defect caused by a cavity in the glue layer meeting the Al film surface.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In-situ LM imaging enabled a comprehensive interpretation of the 90° peel test of Al film on PI substrates. The homogeneity of the peel front supports the use of cohesive elements as a modeling approach. The measured WOS ($\sim 90 \text{ J/m}^2$) was significantly lower as compared to alternative material systems meant for comparable applications, like Cu/TPU and Cu/PDMS [15,16]. Furthermore, measured values include the contribution of the peel arm plasticity, thus they only represent an upper bound for the true interface strength. Such a poor adhesion might not be suitable for stretchable electronics applications. Mechanical interlocking between the Al film and the PI substrate should be pursued to enhance the interface strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Cristian Collini (Microsystems Technology Research Unit, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento, IT) is greatly acknowledged for his contribution as concerns the micro-fabrication of samples. Marc van Maris and Lucien Cleven (Department of Mechanical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, NL) are greatly acknowledged for their technical support in the experimental activity. The "Opto-Digital Technology" grant by OLYMPUS EUROPE Corp. and Quality Manufacturing Today is greatly acknowledged for the loan of the Lext OLS4100 confocal laser microscope, which enabled the ex-situ analysis of the sample surface after peel.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. B. Freund and S. Suresh, *Thin film materials, stress, defect formation and surface evolution*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2003.
- [2] A. A. Volinsky, N. R. Moody and W. W. Gerberich, Interfacial toughness measurements for thin films on substrates, *Acta Materialia*, **50**, 2002, pp. 441-466 ([doi:10.1016/S1359-6454\(01\)00354-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-6454(01)00354-8))
- [3] W. S. Wong and A. Salleo, *Flexible electronics: materials and applications*, Springer, New York, 2009.
- [4] T. Someya, *Stretchable electronics*, Wiley-VCH Verlag & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, 2013.
- [5] S. P. Lacour, J. Jones, Z. Suo and S. Wagner, Design and performance of thin metal film interconnects for skin-like electronic circuits, *Electron Device Letters, IEEE*, **25**, 2004, pp.179-181 ([doi:10.1109/LED.2004.825190](https://doi.org/10.1109/LED.2004.825190))
- [6] D.-H. Kim and J. A. Rogers, Stretchable Electronics: Materials Strategies and Devices. *Advanced Materials*, **20**, 2008, pp. 4887-4892 ([doi:10.1002/adma.200801788](https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.200801788))
- [7] T. Li, Z. Y. Huang, Z. C. Xi, S. P. Lacour, S. Wagner and Z. Suo, Delocalizing strain in a thin metal film on a polymer substrate, *Mechanics of Materials*, **37**, 2005, pp. 261-273 ([doi:10.1016/j.mechmat.2004.02.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mechmat.2004.02.002))
- [8] T. Li and Z. Suo, Ductility of thin metal films on polymer substrates modulated by interfacial adhesion, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **44**, 2007, pp. 1696-1705 ([doi:10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2006.07.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2006.07.022))
- [9] N. Lambrecht, T. Pardoën and S. Yunus, Giant stretchability of thin gold films on rough elastomeric substrates, *Acta Materialia*, **61**, 2013, pp. 540-547, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2012.10.001>)
- [10] J. Zheng, *Interfacial fracture of micro thin film interconnects under monotonic and cyclic loading*, PhD dissertation, Georgia Institute of Technology, 2008
- [11] L. F. Kawashita, D. R. Moore, J. G. Williams, Analysis of peel arm curvature for the determination of fracture toughness in metal-polymer laminates, *Journal of Materials Science*, **40**, 2005, pp. 4541-4548 ([doi:10.1007/s10853-005-0856-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-005-0856-8))
- [12] K. Kendall, Thin-film peeling, the elastic term, *Journal of Physics, D: Applied Physics*, **8**, 1975, pp. 1449-1452 ([doi:10.1088/0022-3727/8/13/005](https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/8/13/005))
- [13] ASTM D3330/D3330M - 04(2010), *Standard Test Method for Peel Adhesion of Pressure-Sensitive Tape*
- [14] G. T. Ostrowicki and S. K. Sitaraman, Magnetically actuated peel test for thin films, *Thin Solid Films*, **520**, 2012, pp. 3987-3993 ([doi:10.1016/j.tsf.2012.01.042](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2012.01.042))
- [15] O. van der Sluis, Y. Y. Hsu, P. H. M. Timmermans, M. Gonzalez and J. P. M. Hoefnagels, Stretching-induced interconnect delamination in stretchable electronic circuits, *Journal of Physics, D: Applied Physics*, **44**, 2011, pp.1-11 ([doi:10.1088/0022-3727/44/3/034008](https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/44/3/034008))
- [16] J. P. M. Hoefnagels, J. Neggels, P. H. M. Timmermans, O. van der Sluis and M. G. D. Geers, Copper-rubber interface delamination in stretchable electronics, *Scripta Materialia*, **63**, 2010 ([doi:10.1016/j.scriptamat.2010.06.041](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scriptamat.2010.06.041))
- [17] M. Elices, G.V. Guinea, J. Gómez and J. Planas, The cohesive zone model: advantages, limitations and challenges, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **69**, 2002, pp. 137-163 ([doi:10.1016/S0013-7944\(01\)00083-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7944(01)00083-2))
- [18] B. G. Vossen, P. J. G. Schreurs, O. van der Sluis and M. G. D. Geers, Multi-scale modeling of delamination through fibrillation, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **66**, 2014, pp. 117-132 ([doi:10.1016/j.jmps.2014.01.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmps.2014.01.009))
- [19] M. Nase, A. Zankel, B. Langer, H. J. Baumann, W. Grellmann and P. Poelt, Investigation of the peel behavior of polyethylene/polybutene-1 peel films using in situ peel tests with environmental scanning electron microscopy, *Polymer*, **49**, 2008, pp. 5458-5466 ([doi:10.1016/j.polymer.2008.10.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2008.10.004))

- [20] R. Lucchini, E. Cattarinuzzi, D. Gastaldi, D. Picononi, L. Lorenzelli, P. Vena, Buckling waves in aluminum on a polyimide sea: In situ analysis towards a reliable design strategy for stretchable electronics, *Materials Today*, in press, 2015 ([doi:10.1016/j.mattod.2015.04.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mattod.2015.04.015))
- [21] E. Cattarinuzzi, R. Lucchini, D. Gastaldi, P. Vena, A. Adami, L. Lorenzelli, Design of aluminum/polyimide stretchable interconnects investigated through in-situ testing, *Proceedings of the 18th AISEM (Associazione Italiana Sensori E Microsistemi) Annual Conference 2015 (Eds. L. Lorenzelli, G. F. Dalla Betta), Trento, Italy, February 3-5, 2015* ([doi:10.1109/AISEM.2015.7066784](https://doi.org/10.1109/AISEM.2015.7066784))
- [22] R. Lucchini, *Mechanics of stretchable interconnects for stretchable electronics devices*, PhD dissertation, Politecnico di Milano, 2014
- [23] A. A. Kinloch, C. C. Lau, J. G. Williams, The peeling of flexible laminates, *International Journal of Fracture*, **66**, 1994, pp. 45-70 ([doi:10.1007/BF00012635](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00012635))